

Pandemic

Developed by: Z-Man Games

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Keywords

Collaborative Problem-solving, Infectious disease, Public Health, Risk Management, Strategic Decision-making

Figure 1. Cover art of *Pandemic* (Z-Man Games). Used for educational review. Rights belong to the publisher.

Introduction

Pandemic (see Figure 1) and its offshoots are collaborative games focused on stopping a global pandemic from spreading. *Pandemic* is not designed as a serious game but has been created and sold to the public as entertainment, which it does well. However, *Pandemic* is an excellent game for simulating complex environments, the spread of infectious disease, and building collaborative and cooperative problem-solving skills. The game was developed by Matt Leacock of Z-Man Games and first released in 2008. New versions in different languages, incorporating new character options and changing the gameplay to reflect persistent changes based on player choices, have been added throughout 2023.

The game's principle uses a random card draw to seed disease around the globe, then adds another deck to infect further and amplify existing diseases. Players have attributes and

actions that they use to slow the progress of the disease while working within the game's random spread mechanics.

Facts

Release date:	2008, 2023
Developer:	Z-Man Games
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–4
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	45 minutes
Languages:	English, Serbian/Croatian, Arabic, Czech, Italian, Ukrainian, Hebrew, Portuguese, Dutch, German, Japanese, Polish, Spanish, Thai, Catalan, Estonian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Chinese, French, Greek, Icelandic, Hungarian, Korean, Danish, Norwegian, Russian, Bulgarian, Finnish, Swedish, Romanian
Environment:	Tabletop
Material:	No additional material required
Price:	\$36–53 CAD

Resonance & Criticism

Pandemic has received critical acclaim and many awards, including Golden Geek Nominations and Winners, Meeples Choice Awards, Hra roku Nominee, Spiel des Jahres Nominees, and BoardGameGeek Hall of Fame Inductee. It is currently ranked 162 overall on BoardGameGeek, based on more than 130,000 ratings.

Game Principle & Process

Pandemic is a real-world simulation game of infectious disease treatment. With random infection and spread procedures and collaborative team play, this game is complex and challenging. The objective is to find cures for four infectious diseases before they become uncontrollable. Players must use their individual character attributes and actions to stop this from happening. There are intrinsic rewards in the game, depending on the version played, as well as carryover effects in newer versions that impact all future games played.

Social interaction is paramount in Pandemic. Without careful planning and strategic cooperation, you will not be successful.

Pandemic is based on the spread of infectious disease and, increasingly, the effective measures for stopping such spread.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

There are two primary learning objectives of Pandemic: the spread of infectious disease and how to contain it, and collaborative and cooperative problem solving. The game's random spread mechanics (decks of cards, Epidemic cards, and Outbreaks) add a sense of realism to gameplay, as uncertainty is prominent. The abilities and actions of each player have both shared and unique components, bringing a sense of ownership, character, and meaning to each play. The game is designed such that without effective collaboration and cooperation, your team will not succeed, and the viruses will win.

Teacher interaction may be necessary for initial rule comprehension and the occasional rule or action interpretation, but the rule book is clear and well-written. There are also many videos available online to teach the gameplay mechanics. In addition, Pandemic homepage (<https://www.zmangames.com/game/pandemic/>) features Pandemic Puzzles that can help orient new players to the challenges of multiplayer cooperation and problem-solving.

Pandemic is an excellent game that requires skill, communication, collaboration, and cooperation to have a chance of success. Even with all of those, the randomness of the infectious spread may still overcome the players, just as in real life.

Effectiveness

No empirical evidence has been found to date on the effectiveness or learning impacts of Pandemic.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Some players may find the topic of a spreading pandemic challenging, especially given real-world COVID-19 experiences. Beyond that, this game is neither ethically challenging nor risky.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Z-Man Games. (n.d.). *Pandemic* [Board game]. Z-Man Games.
<https://www.zmangames.com/game/pandemic/>